

USE OF GAMING TECHNOLOGIES IN INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the role of game technologies in increasing efficiency during training in preschool educational organizations is justified.

Today, new pedagogical technologies and interactive methods are entering the education system, including the preschool education system. One of the urgent problems facing the science of pedagogy is to convey the essence of the content, basic principles, laws and ways of their effective use to practicing educators and teachers. The concept of educational technology means a tool for achieving the educational goal, that is, the step-by-step implementation of a pre-designed educational process based on an integrated system, and the system of methods, methods and tools for achieving this goal, and management of the educational process.

The central problem of pedagogical technology is to ensure the achievement of educational goals through the development of the child's personality. Game technology also differs from the game method by its clear goal, logical sequence and interdependence of the processes to be implemented, and the guarantee of achieving predetermined results.

A child begins to master pedagogical performance games from the age of three. By this age, the child begins to get acquainted with the relationships between people, begins to distinguish between the internal and external aspects of events, and begins to feel internal experiences. He reacts to them. At the preschool age, children master the game activities and begin to prepare for socially valuable and socially valued activities.

There are the following types of pedagogical games used in the preschool education system:

1. Children's mood booster.
2. Invitation to cooperation.
3. Inviting children to express themselves.
4. It is aimed at eliminating physical and intellectual problems, forming a sense of self-confidence in children.

5. Describing limitations in the behavior of preschool children.
6. Gives positive corrections to children's personality structure.
7. Shaper of international tolerance.
8. Games that form social and collective relations in children.

The use of developmental pedagogical games in preschool education in the educational process has the following specific characteristics.

First, developmental pedagogical games consist of a set of special tasks.

Secondly, tasks in the game are carried out using colored cubes, bricks, squares, plasticine, cardboard, constructor-mechanical complexes with the help of various pictures and silent objects.

Thirdly, in order to ensure the independent execution of tasks, it is necessary to ensure their quality execution from easy to difficult, within a certain period of time.

The use of interactive games in preschool educational organizations leads to positive results. During these games, the child turns from a passive object into an active subject. The main task of the teacher is to organize the game and create conditions for children's creativity. In the process of interactive games, the child learns to express his independent opinion correctly, to listen to others, in other words, through interactive games, positive qualities necessary for every child are formed in the future. In order to effectively conduct interactive games, it is necessary to pay attention to the following rules:

1. To determine to what extent the children understood the rules and content of the game before the session.
2. Taking into account the age characteristics of children and their relationships with each other.
3. Taking into account the abilities and psychological characteristics of each child.
4. Use of materials that are interesting to children during the game.
5. Finding styles that attract attention and attention.
6. Correct distribution of roles to children.

A properly organized game from a pedagogical point of view, along with the formation of the child's moral and willful qualities, arouses interest in learning and discovering the secrets of the world around him. Therefore, game technologies should be widely used in preschool education organizations. The concept of game technology is a component of pedagogical technology. Game technology differs from the game method in traditional education by its clear goal, logical sequence and interdependence of the processes to be implemented, and the guarantee of achieving predetermined results.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of the above theoretical foundations serves to increase the effectiveness of the preschool education process. Thus, games are a means of active learning and learning of reality by a child. A child knows the world while playing.

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